

Sustainable Tourism Development and Effect of Radioactive Materials on Environment

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Abstract

Tourism revolves around people of diverse cultural backgrounds. Tourism values the things that are most precious in our world. It can be a catalyst for the local economy, jobs and opportunities. This leads to Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of ecosystems for future. Main reasons why tourists visit a destination are sustainably manage forests, landscapes, biodiversity and natural heritage sites. Sustainable tourism has a huge role not only in preserving biodiversity, but also in respecting earthly ecosystems, due to its efforts towards the reduction of waste and consumption, the conservation of local flora and fauna with its awareness raising activities. Thorium and Uranium are observe in our surroundings, especially coastal area. They are naturally occurring radioactive elements which emit radiations. Though they are better performing fuel material, but it is hazardous for living beings because of its harmful radiations. Solutions Thorium and Uranium in water samples are tested and resulted in dangerous for human beings. Their radiation can cause cancer, brain tumor, skin disease. More exposure to those radiation leads to the death.

Keywords – *sustainable, ecosystems, biodiversity, exposure, radioactive Materials.*

Introduction :

Tourism is an important tool for economic development for the world. This industry is totally depends upon mankind which provide jobs. A healthy environment is essential to attract worldwide tourists. The basic needs like transportation, affordable accommodation, safety and security, drinkable water, banking and commination services must available. Tourism sector in India is unique endowments of ecosystems having rivers, mountains, forests, vallies, rich culture and heritage. United Nations declared 2017 as the International year of sustainable tourism for development.

Discussion :

Sustainable tourism leaves a minimum negative impact on the places visited and preferably rather leaves a positive impact on society. Tourism is also identified as one of the major tools of the economy. —World set a goal to increase the economic benefits to developing and developed countries by 2030,.|| **Sustainable tourism leads to meet the needs of tourist and the tourism industry. It gives opportunities without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.**

Fundamentals for sustainable tourism Development

- 1. Use of resources sustainably :** The use of resources conservative and sustainably makes long-term business sense. Such as natural, social and cultural resources. **Integrating biodiversity with tree plantation and conservation of wildlife program.**
- 2. Tourism planning :** Tourism development comes under the framework of local to global strategic planning. It also has a everlasting impact which increases the viability of tourism. The bridge between

the tourism industry and local communities is required if they have to grow. respect for the natural, social and cultural environment depends on quality Marketing that provide information of destination areas.

3. To grow local economy : Tourism supports wide range of local economic activities. It affects values or cost which protects these economy. This also avoids environmental damage to increase quality of the tourism experience. The involvement of local communities in the tourism benefits them and the environment.

4. Reducing overconsumption : Reduction waste avoids the costs of restoring long-term environmental damage and contributes to the quality of tourism to build preferable environment.

Sustainability is about the protection of the environment. However, there is far more to the environment than just the natural landscape. Tourism makes use of natural resources, such as clean air, land, mineral waters, and the water in lakes and seas. Survey shows that the water of the coastal areas is naturally contaminated with Thorium and Uranium, available in the form of salts. These dissolve into water and make soil and water pollution in vegetables and food. Radiations from those are harmful to the living organisms. They are toxic and can cause damage to internal organs. drinking massive amounts of thorium and Uranium can cause metal poisoning

Conclusion :

Healthy environment is required for tourism development. This research paper aims to focus on development of environment in the area of tourism. India is identified as religious and natural tourism. Sustainability is about the life long protection of the environment. Over the recent years, human activities on environment and climate exponentially increased, hence it is importance to preserve sustainable tourism. In 2019, Tourism industry accounted for 10.4 percent of the total worldwide GDP.

Limited use of thorium and uranium is not harmful to the human beings. It provides fuel to the country and helps to overcome the fuel crises which strengthen the economy. Small amount of thorium and uranium salts dissolved into the water and soil leads to the nuclear pollution. However the massive amount of exposure of those materials at tourist places can cause to damage health and biodiversity.

Environment Protection programs are aiming at reducing risks to the nature from contaminants such as hazardous materials and wastes. They provide the required actions to be taken in the event of a spill or release. Lots of environmental degradation is irreversible or will take hundreds of years to fix hence Conservation of the environment is necessary.

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